

IMPORTANT PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF ARCHITECTURAL SOLUTIONS IN
THE DEVELOPMENT OF PILGRIMAGE TOURISM .

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Abstract: In this article, decisions and decrees issued in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of pilgrimage development. Important architectural elements of the concept and principles of the development of pilgrimage objects in the world. Principles and methods of master plans of architectural solutions. It included issues such as the introduction of design principles using a variety of methods in order to cover the subject more broadly.

Keywords: radius, Sarigorgon, religious tourism, open exhibition areas, mandatory greening, distance radius.

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Introduction

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 9, 2021 "On measures to further develop domestic and pilgrimage tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-6165, the creation of necessary conditions for pilgrims has reached an important stage. It defines the following tasks.

Creating plans for the priority restoration of cultural heritage objects used in pilgrimage tourism routes in 2021-2025 ;

Creation and implementation of a "Roadmap" for receiving foreign tourists from far abroad and neighboring republics and creating favorable conditions for them. It paved the way for the implementation of large-scale works to give special attention to architectural solutions and master plans.[1]

Cultural heritage objects with high tourism potential, which are planned to create conditions for visitors

Table 1

No	Name of the object	Address
Fergana region		
1.	Shrine "Hazrat Khizr Kadamjolari".	Rishton district, "Bo'ston" MFY
2.	"Yigit Pirim" shrine	Uchkoprik district, "Olmurod" neighborhood
3.	"Satkak Azizlar" shrine	"Satkak" MFY, Fergana district
4.	"Puri Siddique" shrine	Margilan city, "Yurmadoz" MFY

5.	"Burkhaniddin Marginani monument" complex	City of Margilan, "Pichakhchi" MFY
6.	"Moyi Mubarak" shrine	Kokan city, "Nurafshon" MFY, "Sarmazor" cemetery
7.	"Huwaydo" shrine	"Chimyon" MFY, Fergana district

Measures to be taken in shrines:

1. Current maintenance of roads leading to shrines;
2. Installation of road signs and information signs leading to the shrine from the regional center and other large settlements;
3. Launch a convenient traffic plan for tourists to enter and exit the shrine without queues;
4. Establishment of separate parking lots for vehicles (cars and buses);
5. Development and implementation of plans for distributing the flow of pilgrims throughout the facility in case of queues and traffic jams, as well as emergency situations;
6. Development and implementation of a scheme for placing pilgrims in the process of organizing prayer ceremonies (prayers);

Priority restoration of cultural heritage objects used in tourism routes in 2021-2025

Table 2

T/r	Name of the object	Established period	Address
Fergana region			
1.	"Sarigorgon" archaeological monument	Mil. I century BC - I AD - VII-VIII centuries	Uchkoprik district, "Sarigorgon" MFY
2.	Shrine of "Hazrat Ali Shahimardon".	20th century	"Yordon" MFY, Fergana district
3.	"Khojam Podshah" shrine	XVIII century	"Birdamlik" MFY, Fergana district

Definition and types of religious tourism :

A tourist traveling for religious purposes is a person who is outside the country of permanent residence for a period of not more than six months to visit holy places and religious centers. Religious tourism should be understood as activities related to providing services and meeting the needs of tourists traveling to holy places and religious centers outside the usual environment.[2]

Pilgrimage objects of the world countries

Table 1

Most important Christian centers abroad	
Pilgrimage	Country
Vatican	Italy
Lady of Lourdes	France
Holy Land	Israel
Mecca	Saudi Arabia
Agia (Saint) Sophia	Turkey
Cappadocia	Asia Minor - Turkey

Destinations of internationally recognized religious tourism objects are now a constant center of analysis.

Table 2

Famous international religious tourism destinations
Famous religious tourist destinations worldwide
Vatican City (Italy)
Santiago de Compostela (Spain)
Lourdes (France)
Mount Athos (Greece)
Jerusalem (Israel)
Medjugorje (Bosnia – Herzegovina)
Haifa's Bahá'í Gardens (India)

Religious tourism is divided into two main types:

- pilgrimage tourism;
- religious tourism of excursion and educational direction.

In pilgrimage tourism, spiritual pilgrimage tourism stands out.

Types and characteristics of pilgrimage

In science, several types of pilgrimage are usually classified according to different criteria:

- 1) according to the number and family affiliation of the participants - individual, family and collective pilgrimage;
- 2) by duration - long and short-term pilgrimages (previously, according to Russian Orthodox laws, a trip lasting more than 10 days was considered a pilgrimage).[3]

Methods.

Each field has important methods of study, and there are criteria that play an important role in shaping the architecture of shrines. Constantly fulfilling the architectural criteria serves as the development of the tourism industry, which is growing day by day. Methods of developing the architecture of shrines in Uzbekistan:

pilgrimage sites of districts and cities consists of the research of the architectural objects, architectural urban planning solutions of the existing pilgrimage sites, the development of project proposals, and the scientific identification of the places of interest among the people;

Cities and districts z is to analyze the current state of pilgrimage sites, to find, develop and implement effective solutions and ways to improve pilgrimage sites based on the study and generalization of modern achievements and experiences gained in the region and abroad;

study the experiences of creating historical forms of pilgrimage objects in cities and districts ;

Analysis of the experiences of each city and district and foreign countries in creating modern forms of design of pilgrimage facilities;[4]

Scientific identification, justification and determination of new directions for the design of objects of pilgrimage;

Development of scientific-theoretical and design proposals for the practical application of new directions of pilgrimage sites;

tourism in cities and districts , full restoration of spiritual values and customs, which are intangible wealth of the population . Preservation and restoration of architectural fashion assets, their spiritual and economic effective use even today;[5]

Historical sources of pilgrimage objects, special scientific literature, graphic materials, miniatures, and ancient traditional dwellings that have been preserved until now are studied, scientifically analyzed, compared using a graphoanalytical method, summarizing them and developing scientific conclusions, theoretical and project proposals based on this.

Results

The historic preservation element of pilgrimage sites seeks to integrate with other elements of the master plan. Historic district towns, buildings, structures and archaeological sites are closely related and irreversible. Related to past, present and future land use, housing, public facilities planning and historic preservation. Historical monuments and shrines strive to find a balance between, on the one hand, the preservation, use and interpretation of Uzbekistan's important historical resources, and, on the other hand, society's need for permanent changes in the use of land and shrines. In order to preserve the valuable image and unique architecture of shrines in our country, it is necessary to increase the criteria and elements of the master plans as an unchangeable golden rule.

Workshops;

Open exhibition areas;

Indoor exhibition spaces;

National cuisine teahouses, cafes, restaurants;

Recreational resorts;

Mandatory greening areas;

Figure 1. E-Chor-Bag; 1- Majid Shah; 2-Lotfoll Mosque; 3 - cathedral mosque; 4th Mosque Dli; 5-Ali Kapu; 6- Chekhel-Sutui; 7- Khakht-Behishg, 8- windowed porch; 9th week powder; 10th madrasa and caravanserai Mezeri-Shah; 11 - Marnun Bridge 12 - Allavsrdi Khan Bridge; 13-akvsduk, 14-Pols-Khalju.

In the master plans of the pilgrimage facilities, it is necessary to establish mandatory greening and planting areas. In particular, in the concept of introducing the green space program in the Pilgrimage areas, it is necessary to develop separate rules for the city centers and for the district centers. Mandatory greening for a place of pilgrimage located within a radius of 500-1000 meters from the city center for up to 50 years, for a place of pilgrimage located within a radius of 1000-2000 meters from the city center for up to 40 years, for a radius of 2000-4000 meters up to 30 years, and for all places of pilgrimage beyond a radius of 4000 meters It is necessary to strive for the establishment of green areas, which must be preserved for up to 25 years.

Figure 2. 1. Drum Tower 2 Imperial Pools (Si Yuan) 3 Purple City 4. Bell Tower. Tower 5 Temple of Ancestors 6. Altar of Gods 7 Door of Heavenly Peace 8 Door of High Spirit 9. Temple of Heaven 10. Temple of Agriculture

For districts, unlike cities, it is necessary to add 10 years for each distance radius. For example, mandatory green spaces up to 50 years are supposed to be set for 60 years, and for 40 years - 50 years. The ever-changing landscape design of green spaces cannot be limited to changes in the shape of the earth's surface. Only in the districts, it is necessary to control that the green space allotted to 1000 square meters does not decrease from 1000 square meters even if the shape of the land plot changes. As a result, the visiting pilgrim can see and enjoy not only the exterior, but also the ancient appearance of the landscape architecture.

Summary

It is necessary to preserve the historical aspects of pilgrimage objects and to constantly fill their protected areas. In our country, it is important to reflect the conceptual projects of shrines, local customs, traditions and values in buildings. Enriching the elements of the protected zones, the green space program should be adopted as a mandatory project for architectural solutions. In this article, it is considered important to harmonize the principles of tourist accommodation with the experiences of other countries based on local conditions. The small scale design of the workshop and shop exhibition pavilions is consistent with the visual learning objectives for the visiting pilgrims to explore the historical sources of the regions. The design of power units in convenient places through small architectural spatial constructions creates a number of conveniences. In the principles of the architecture of pilgrimage objects, it is important to strive to develop the basics of comfort, protection from environmental damage, the most effective solutions in functional solutions, and the design that leaves reasons for repeated visits.

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